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Understanding the Essence of Resilience: Guidance Heads Navigating Professional Demands

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Abstract

This phenomenological study navigates guidance heads into their resiliency. Three guidance heads in the Philippines were selected as research participants by employing purposive sampling technique. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Overall, 9 themes were gathered. The result revealed the following (3) themes on the live experiences: (1) demonstrate resilient leadership amidst various constraints and challenges, (2) empowering student-centered support, and (3) seeking innovative solutions to ensure practical guidance for students. On the coping strategies, there were three (3) themes emerged namely: (1) prioritize efficient resource management, (2) maintain a balanced approach and promote teamwork, and (3) manage stress effectively, maintaining work-life balance. On their insights; there are three (3) themes emerged namely: (1) role responsibilities and challenges, (2) personal fulfillment and motivation and (3) impact on students and community. The general implication of the results refined to the need to further improve the resiliency of the guidance heads. Finally, this serves as a basis for guidance heads in initiating intervention programs for guidance counselors to improve being resilient.

Keywords: *resilience, guidance heads, phenomenology, Philippines*

Introduction

Guidance is assistance provided to individuals by an expert (Evi, 2020). Guidance in principle is a process of providing assistance carried out by an expert to a person or several individuals in terms of understanding them-selves, connecting understanding of themselves with the environment, choosing, determining, and planning according to their self-concept and demands based on applicable norms (Utomo, 2022). While counseling is a process of providing assistance carried out through counseling interviews by an expert (called a counselor) to individuals who are experiencing a problem (called clients) which leads to the resolution of the problems faced by the client (Sukatin et al., 2022). Moreover, counseling is a series of the most basic activities of guidance to help counsel/clients face-to-face with the aim that clients can take responsibility for various specific problems or problems (Prayogi et al., 2023).

Despite the efforts to enhance resilience through guidance systems, Asia faces several challenges. One significant issue is the disparity in access to quality education and guidance services between urban and rural areas. Rural regions often lack adequate educational infrastructure, qualified teachers, and counseling services, leading to a gap in the development of resilience skills among students (UNESCO, 2020). Another challenge is the cultural stigma associated with seeking psychological help. In many Asian societies, mental health issues are often stigmatized, preventing individuals from accessing necessary support and guidance (Lee et al., 2017). This stigma can lead to untreated mental health conditions, reducing overall resilience.

Many schools in the Philippines, particularly in rural areas, face significant resource constraints. This includes a lack of trained counselors, inadequate facilities, and limited access to continuing education for counseling professionals. According to Tan (2013), these limitations hinder the delivery of effective guidance and counseling services. A study by Alonto (2018) found that in public schools, a single counselor often serves several hundred students, making it challenging to provide personalized guidance and support. Reducing the administrative burden on guidance counselors by streamlining paperwork and providing administrative support can allow counselors to focus more on student interactions (Torres, 2016). Schools should invest in improving counseling facilities and resources. This includes creating private spaces for counseling sessions, providing up-to-date materials, and ensuring access to mental health resources (Martinez, 2019).

The Philippines has only 4,069 registered Guidance Counselors as of June 2022, far below the desired ratio of 1:500 for its 27.4 million students. This shortage, with only 19% of authorized positions filled, leaves a vast gap in essential mental health support, overburdening the existing counselors with academic and mental health responsibilities, leading to exhaustion and burnout (Chi, 2023). As of May 2020, the Department of Education (DepEd) has only 1,096 active counselors for about 20 million public school students, making the recommended 1:500 ratio unattainable. Despite over 5,398 open positions, only 20% have been filled, primarily due to low compensation.

While the shortage of guidance counselors in the Philippines is well-documented, there is limited research on the resilience of these counselors. Specifically, studies are needed to understand how guidance counselors cope with the high demands and pressures of their roles, the strategies they use to maintain their well-being, and the support systems that can help them avoid burnout. Additionally, exploring the impact of counselor resilience on the quality of student support and outcomes can provide valuable insights for improving guidance services. Further research could also examine the long-term effects of inadequate counselor support on the mental health and academic performance of students, particularly in rural areas with severe resource constraints.

This study aims to explore the true essence of resilience by examining the real-life experiences of guidance heads in the field of education. These individuals play a crucial role in dealing with various challenges in their everyday work. Through analyzing their stories, perspectives, and coping strategies, the goal of this research is to gain insight into how they handle difficulties and continue to demonstrate resilience.

Ultimately, the findings of this study are expected to inform the development of targeted support programs and interventions designed to the specific needs of guidance heads. By shedding light on their lived experiences, this research seeks to enhance the professional well-being and effectiveness of guidance heads, benefiting both these individuals and the educational institutions they work with.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of the guidance heads as they navigate the professional demands of their position?
2. What are your coping strategies to manage the demands of your position?
3. What are the insights of the guidance heads regarding the demands of their position?

Methodology

Research Design

This qualitative research incorporates phenomenological design (Maponya, 2020) in understanding the essence of resilience in the lived experiences of guidance heads in navigating professional demands. As Bakioğlo et al., (2022) emphasized phenomenological design provides researchers with a way to describe content-rich comprehension of experience. A phenomenological design was preferred by the researchers to gather some common shared experiences of academics in different contexts in different universities. Similarly, Creswell (2012) defined this design as “describing the meaning for several individuals of their lived (or shared) experiences or a phenomenon”. In a phenomenological study understanding regarding the phenomenon is elicited as cited by (Bakioğlo et al., 2022) and insight is gained by interviewing knowledgeable participants (Coy, 2019). Therefore, this study was designed to explore academics' perceptions of their emotional state during their time at universities.

Many scholars in phenomenology hold the view that human beings extract meaning from the world through personal experience (Husserl, 1931; Hycner, 1985; Koopmans, 2015; Hourigan and Edgar, 2020; Gasparyan, 2021). The general qualitative methodology of social science research has shaped phenomenology as a methodological approach just as reliable as quantitative and experimental methods, as recently discussed by Høffding et al. (2022), who stressed the advantages of phenomenology in qualitative research (see also Zahavi, 2019a,b).

Participants

Following Creswell's (2013) guidance, a reasonable sample size ranging from 3 to 25 participants will be targeted for inclusion in the study. The informants will consist of guidance heads from three distinct educational institutions across the Philippines: Far Eastern University in Manila, University of Cebu in Cebu City, and PHINMA Cagayan De Oro College in Cagayan de Oro. The selection of these institutions aims to capture a diverse range of perspectives and experiences within different educational contexts. Guidance heads meeting the criteria of substantial tenure in their positions, demonstrated experience in navigating professional demands, and willingness to participate voluntarily will be invited to partake in semi-structured interviews.

Instrument

The researchers will employ a phenomenological approach with purposive sampling to investigate the essence of resilience among guidance heads navigating professional demands. Interview guides, and audio recording devices will be utilized to collect and analyze data.

These interviews will delve into the lived experiences, perceptions, and strategies related to resilience among guidance heads, to uncover meaningful insights that contribute to a deeper understanding of resilience within the context of educational leadership. Through the systematic utilization of research materials and purposive sampling, this study endeavors to shed light on the nuanced dynamics of resilience among guidance heads, informing practices and interventions aimed at supporting their professional growth and well-being.

Procedure

The data collection process will involve interviewing participants based on the research questions formulated by the researchers. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted to explore the lived experiences, perceptions, and strategies related to resilience among guidance heads navigating professional demands. The interview questions, aligned with the research objectives, will guide the conversation and facilitate in-depth exploration of key themes and insights. Each interview will be conducted in a conducive and confidential setting, ensuring participants feel comfortable sharing their experiences openly. To ensure the accuracy and completeness of data, digital audio recording devices will be utilized to fully capture the responses of the participants during the interviews. These

recordings will serve as primary sources of data, enabling detailed analysis and interpretation of the participants' narratives. Additionally, transcription will be employed to transcribe the audio recordings into written text, facilitating a thorough review and analysis of the data. By leveraging these research methodologies, the data collection process aims to gather rich and comprehensive insights into the essence of resilience among guidance heads, contributing to a deeper understanding of this phenomenon within the context of educational leadership.

Data Analysis

A view of Mohajan (2018) is that qualitative research data analysis entails the searching for patterns in data that are recurrent behavior. This research study on understanding the essence of resilience among guidance heads navigating professional demands will involve a systematic approach to uncover meaningful insights from the collected data. Initially, the transcription of audio recordings will be conducted using transcription manually, converting the spoken interviews into written text for easier manipulation and analysis. Using this method, researchers first watch or listen to recordings to code for nonverbal cues, followed by a stage of notetaking and coding based on pre-defined themes and matching these with time codes and nonverbal cues.

Finally, researchers then transcribe specific quotes of interest from the recording (Parameswaran et al., 2020). The transcribed data will then be organized and labeled according to participant identifiers and interview questions to facilitate clarity and reference during analysis. Thematic coding will be employed as the primary method of analysis, allowing for the identification of recurring patterns, themes, and categories within the data. An inductive approach will be utilized initially to allow themes to emerge directly from the data without imposing preconceived categories, ensuring a grounded and data-driven analysis process. Codes will be systematically applied to segments of text representing meaningful concepts, experiences, or insights related to resilience among guidance heads. These codes will then be grouped to form preliminary themes, reflecting commonalities and variations in the participants' experiences.

Throughout the analysis process, the research team will engage in thorough data familiarization, coding, and theme development, iteratively refining and revising the coding scheme and thematic framework as new insights emerge. Cross-case analysis will be conducted to compare and contrast themes across different participants and institutions, providing insights into the generalizability and variability of the identified themes. Finally, member checking will be employed to validate the preliminary findings by allowing participants to review and provide feedback on the identified themes and interpretations, enhancing the credibility and trustworthiness of the analysis. The final analysis findings will be documented in a comprehensive research report, presenting the key themes, illustrative quotes, interpretations, and implications for theory, practice, and future research.

Ethical Considerations

Research ethics deals primarily with the interaction between researchers and the people they study. This only means that whenever research is conducted on people, their well-being must be our top priority. However, this study took a different route as this is a corpus-driven one. Here, it considered the following: social value, privacy and confidentiality of information, qualification of a researcher, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement (Philippine Health Research Ethics Board, 2017).

Social Value. Ensuring that the research contributes meaningfully to the broader societal understanding of resilience and the experiences of guidance heads in navigating professional demands within private college institutions. This entails demonstrating the relevance and significance of the study beyond academic or personal interests. This encompasses not only the participants but also other stakeholders such as colleagues, administrators, and the broader community affected by the research findings. Upholding social values requires ensuring that the research design, data collection, analysis, and dissemination are conducted in a manner that respects diversity, promotes inclusivity, and mitigates any potential harm or exploitation. Furthermore, it involves prioritizing transparency, accountability, and integrity in all interactions and decisions throughout the research process, thereby fostering trust and upholding the ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice within the social fabric of the research endeavor.

Privacy and confidentiality of information. In adherence to the Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher will ensure that the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents will be protected. Any hard copies containing personal information and the responses of the respondents will be shredded once scanned, encoded, and uploaded accessible to the researcher alone. The data presentation will not include personal information which may lead to the identification of the respondents. Further, once the study is done, the researcher will permanently delete the soft copies to prevent the data from possible risks of a breach of confidentiality.

Qualification as a Researcher. The researcher is qualified to undertake the study. As registered guidance counselors and licensed professional teachers pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy in Education majoring in counseling, the researchers are entrusted with a significant responsibility to ensure the ethical conduct of their research endeavors. This includes demonstrating proficiency in research methodologies, data collection techniques, and ethical guidelines specific to counseling and education. Moreover, the researchers should maintain ongoing professional development, staying abreast of current trends, best practices, and ethical standards within their respective fields. By upholding their qualifications and adhering to professional standards, the researchers contribute to the credibility, validity, and integrity of the research findings, thereby upholding the ethical principles of competence, integrity, and accountability in their scholarly pursuits.

Adequacy of Facilities. The institution has electronic resources from the margins to the center like ProQuest, which is of great

contribution to forming my Review of Related Literature. Of course, the institution has its own ethics committee, which ensures the ethical standards and scientific merit of research involving human subjects. Also, I have a good internet connection, and I have access to online resources/databases such as ProQuest, Philippine E-Journals, Sage Journals, Oxford References, ePlatform, ACMDL Digital Library, and ProQuest Ebook Central.

Community Involvement. As researchers investigating the lived experiences of guidance heads navigating professional demands within private college institutions, it is essential to recognize the integral role that the community plays in shaping and contextualizing the research. This involves actively seeking input, feedback, and participation from relevant community members, including guidance heads, administrators, faculty, students, and other stakeholders impacted by the research. By fostering a collaborative approach, researchers can ensure that the research design, data collection methods, and interpretation of findings are culturally sensitive, relevant, and reflective of the community's perspectives and needs. Furthermore, community involvement promotes transparency, trust, and mutual respect, thereby enhancing the ethical integrity of the research process and fostering a sense of ownership and empowerment among community members regarding the outcomes and implications of the research.

Results and Discussion

This section contains the interview data presented in tabular form so that readers can quickly grasp how the final themes were derived. Moreover, the tables contain core ideas and themes based on the study's objectives. Additionally, some points from the interviews, literature review, and findings of previous studies support the discussions made herein.

The interview results were coded and organized into categories, with similar codes grouped. After the coding, follow the theme development process by pooling categories of the same pattern. Ultimately, the final themes were abstracted. All three tables contain the same process derivations congruent with the research questions, and each contains three themes with three core ideas.

What are the lived experiences of the guidance heads as they navigate the professional demands of their position?

The study presents the lived experiences of guidance heads. There are three themes with three core ideas each. the following themes emerged: (1) demonstrate resilient leadership amidst various constraints and challenges, (2) empowering student-centered support, and (3) seeking innovative solutions to ensure practical guidance for students.

Table 1 shows the different core ideas that expound on each of the three essential themes.

Table 1. *Lived Experiences of Guidance Heads*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Resilient Leadership Amidst Various Constraints and Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strike a balance between work and other duties while working with limited resources and compensation challenges • find new ways of doing things, such as tapping into various counseling services and playing different roles across disciplines to deal with many student-to-counselor ratios and multiple obligations • flexible, resilient, and strategic in managing staff under them or the students they teach
Empowering Student-Centered Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strive for work-life balance amidst complex responsibilities, conflicts, and resource constraints, focusing on delivering personalized student support • manage demanding counselor-to-student ratios, navigate diverse responsibilities, and implement effective scheduling practices to prevent overlaps and ensure optimal support • emphasize the importance of dedication, innovation, and a student-centric approach in achieving work-life harmony and maximizing impact
Seek Innovative Solutions to Ensure Practical Guidance for their Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use everything at hand – for example, certified advisors and students trained to counsel and interns –to offer high-quality aid • embrace opportunities beyond traditional roles, such as consultancy and psychology, to enhance professional growth and impact • implement strategic management practices, including proper scheduling and resource allocation, to optimize student support and operational efficiency

Resilient Leadership Amidst Various Constraints and Challenges

These people make use of their expertise to create a learning atmosphere where pupils can flourish intellectually, socially, and emotionally. They promote innovation and good adjustments that result in teaching excellence by fostering staff collaboration. Below are some examples to justify the results expressed above:

Educational leaders often juggle multiple responsibilities and deal with a myriad of challenges. As mentioned by Participant 2,

"Challenging in then in term of like, not necessarily dealing with co-counselor, its more on really maintaining the monitoring, yung sa supervision." (Challenging in then in term of like, not necessarily dealing with co-counselor, its more on really maintaining the

monitoring, especially in supervision.)

The breadth of their responsibilities is extensive. This captures the range of duties that leaders must manage, requiring a resilient approach to ensure all tasks are effectively handled. As participant 2 succinctly put it,

"Supervising other tasks." (Supervising other tasks.)

For instance, this indicates the extensive scope of responsibilities, with leaders managing multiple branches and departments effectively. Participant 1 shared,

"Handling the FEU Manila and Makati, ginagawa ng VP kunwari VP for Admission, VP for guidance so parang hahawakan na namin ang iba't ibang branch." (Handling the FEU Manila and Makati, the VP is supposed to be VP for Admission, VP for guidance so it seems like we will be handling the different branches.)

The logistical challenges of managing multiple branches and school calendars further complicate their roles. Participant 3 shared,

"3 branches and 2 school calendars so medyo ano talaga when it comes to scheduling activities, we need to schedule para walang overlapping of activities." (We have 3 branches and 2 school calendars, so we need to schedule carefully to avoid overlapping activities).

This necessitates meticulous planning and coordination to avoid conflicts and ensure smooth operations. Additionally, frequent meetings and reporting responsibilities add to the complexity of their roles, participant 3 said,

"More heavy are those administrative functions. In a day, I have three or four meetings and more because, of course, being the head, you have a boss under the student services." (Administrative functions weigh heavily. I typically have three or four meetings per day, sometimes more, as the head overseeing student services.)

Seeking permission and collaboration across borders is also crucial. This showcases the cross-cultural and international dimensions of their roles, necessitating diplomacy and adherence to different regulatory standards. Participant 1 mentioned,

"Nagpaalam ako kay Rosli, Si Capt Rosli, siya yung president ng Brunei counseling... am I allowed to counsel Brunei students because we have a branch?" (I asked permission to Rosli, Captain Rosli, who is the president of the Brunei Counseling... Am I allowed to counsel Brunei students because we have a branch?)

Engagement with various stakeholders is essential. Leaders frequently interact with faculty and administrators. The participant 1 noted, underscoring the collaborative efforts needed to maintain and enhance educational partnerships,

"Nag to-talk ka rin minsan sa mga faculty, ini-invite ka ng academic development or invite ka ng mga administrators... partnerships namin sa DepEd, sa CHED, mga feeder schools," (You also engage in talks with faculty, get invited by academic development or administrators... we have partnerships with DepEd, CHED, feeder schools.)

Resource constraints pose significant challenges. This illustrates the severe understaffing issues, with a disproportionate counselor-to-student ratio that necessitates innovative and resilient leadership to manage effectively. Despite these constraints, the leaders' commitment to their roles and the fulfillment derived from their work remain evident. Highlighting the workload and the necessity of adapting to evolving demands. Participant 1 lamented,

"Kulang ang counselors namin... ang counselors ko 15 lang... we have 25,000 students." (We have a shortage of counselors... I only have 15 counselors... we have 25,000 students.)

"Maraming trabaho... core process mo for a director only for a branch, hindi na nangyayari yun," (There's a lot of work... the core processes for a director at just one branch, that doesn't happen anymore.)

Balancing administrative duties with professional practice is a common theme. This dual role requires effective time management and resilience to handle both counseling duties and administrative functions. As Participant 2 shared,

"Although I am a head but I am also ah para bang practicing my profession in counseling as a counselor." (Although I am a head, I am also practicing my profession in counseling as a counselor.)

Despite the heavy administrative load, leaders remain committed to student-centered support. The additional tasks, such as managing accreditations and preparing reports, are crucial for maintaining standards that ultimately benefit students. As a Participant 2 explained,

"Other plus plus pa nga responsibilities given to you, like mga accreditations, PAASCU, reports, and everything." (Other additional responsibilities given to you, like accreditations, PAASCU, reports, and everything else.)

Monitoring and managing the behavior of counselors is another critical aspect of their role. Ensuring ethical practice and providing oversight supports a professional and student-focused environment, reflecting the leaders' commitment to maintaining high standards. Participant 2 stated,

"Monitoring your counselors. Manage some behavioral concerns of the counselors just to ensure that we are really compliant with basically the ethics in practicing our profession." (Monitoring your counselors. Manage some behavioral concerns of the counselors just to ensure that we are really compliant with basically the ethics in practicing our profession.)

Leaders often have to develop innovative solutions to navigate their complex roles. One approach mentioned was ensuring compliance with ethical standards through regular monitoring. This proactive approach reinforces a culture of professionalism and adherence to ethical standards. Participant 2 added,

"Just to ensure that we are really compliant with basically the ethics in practicing our profession." (Just to ensure that we are really compliant with basically the ethics in practicing our profession.)

Hence, managing multiple responsibilities effectively requires innovative scheduling and time management strategies. Leaders need flexibility and adaptability to handle extensive administrative tasks, frequent meetings, and their professional practice. This part explores the lived experiences of resilient leaders in educational settings, highlighting their challenges, innovative solutions, and dedication to empowering student-centered support.

Empowering Student-Centered Support

The lack of guidance counselors makes guidance directors' administrative responsibilities more difficult because they must also provide student counseling. Importantly, guidance directors carry out their duties with a student-centered mindset.

Empowering and supporting students emerged as a critical priority for leaders in educational settings highlighting the dedication to advocating for students' needs and ensuring their well-being, fostering long-term loyalty and positive relationships. Participant 1 emphasized,

"You fight for them, hindi mo sila iniwan and that's very important... they will love you forever," (You fight for them, you don't leave them, and that's very important... they will love you forever)

This theme also encompassed discussions on the importance of providing adequate compensation and support for staff indicating that competitive salaries are key to supporting and retaining staff. As a participant 1 mentioned,

"Yung salary nila, yung buhay nila... mataas salary nila," (Their salary, their lives... their salary is high.)

Personal fulfillment was a recurring topic, with leaders expressing satisfaction from their impact on students' lives underscoring the intrinsic rewards of their profession despite the associated stress. Participant 3 stated,

"I feel fulfilled when I see the positive impact of my guidance on a student's future," (I feel fulfilled when I see the positive impact of my guidance on a student's future,)

Effective leadership traits were also highlighted, including charisma, decision-making skills, and the ability to innovate. Stressing the personal attributes necessary for successful leadership. An participant 1 noted,

"Personality mo, you have to have charisma... good in decision making," (Your personality, you have to have charisma... good in decision-making)

Leaders in educational settings often juggle multiple responsibilities and face myriad challenges highlighting the complexity of supervisory roles where maintaining effective oversight can be more demanding than direct interactions with colleagues. This requires a resilient approach to ensure all tasks are effectively handled. Participant 3 noted,

"Challenging in terms of not necessarily dealing with co-counselors, it's more on really maintaining the monitoring, yung sa supervision," (Challenging in terms of not necessarily dealing with co-counselors, it's more about really maintaining the monitoring, in supervision)

The logistical challenges of managing multiple branches and school calendars further complicate their roles. As the participant 3 shared,

"3 branches and 2 school calendars so medyo ano talaga when it comes to scheduling to activities, we need to schedule para walang overlapping of activities." (We have 3 branches and 2 school calendars, so we need to schedule carefully to avoid overlapping activities)

This necessitates meticulous planning and coordination to avoid conflicts and ensure smooth operations. Despite the heavy administrative load, leaders remain committed to student-centered support, with additional tasks such as managing accreditations and preparing reports being crucial for maintaining standards that benefit students. Participant 2 noted,

"Other plus plus pa nga responsibilities given to you, like mga accreditations, PAASCU, reports, and everything." (Other additional responsibilities given to you, like accreditations, PAASCU, reports, and everything else.)

Monitoring and managing the behavior of counselors is another critical aspect of their role. Ensuring ethical practice and providing oversight supports a professional and student-focused environment, reflecting the leaders' commitment to maintaining high standards.

Participant 2 explained,

"Monitoring your counselors. Manage some behavioral concerns of the counselors just to ensure that we are compliant with basically the ethics in practicing our profession." (Monitoring your counselors. Manage some behavioral concerns of the counselors just to ensure that we are compliant with basically the ethics in practicing our profession.)

Therefore, empowering and supporting students is a top priority for educational leaders, who emphasize advocacy, positive relationships, and staff support through competitive salaries and personal fulfillment. Key leadership traits include charisma, decision-making, and innovation, along with managing extensive administrative tasks and complex supervisory roles. Despite logistical challenges, leaders are committed to meticulous planning, ethical practice, and maintaining high standards to benefit students.

Seeking Innovative Solutions to Ensure Practical Guidance for Students

In order to guarantee that their students receive enlightening counsel, the chiefs of guidance are constantly looking for novel concepts. Through their mentorship programs, they match up students with seasoned professionals from a variety of industries who may advise them on the best path for their career choices. These mentors' ideas, insights, and networking opportunities are very beneficial to these individuals.

Innovation emerged as a crucial component of effective leadership in educational settings. Leaders described various innovative approaches to addressing challenges, such as maximizing the use of peer facilitators and interns due to the lack of psychometrician positions showcasing creative solutions to staffing shortages. Participant 1 explained,

"We don't have items for psychometricians. So mina-maximize naming ay peer facilitators at tsaka interns," (We don't have items for psychometricians. So we maximize peer facilitators and interns)

The importance of work-life integration was also highlighted, illustrating the balancing act between professional responsibilities and personal commitments. Participant 1 shared,

"Saturday and Sunday are really sacred for me... I do community work, that gratis a diyos," (Saturday and Sunday are really sacred for me... I do community work, that's gratis to God)

Additionally, preemptive communication before traveling abroad, as one leader described, underscores the proactive strategies employed to maintain productivity and personal well-being. Participant 1 added,

"before we fly abroad, I email all the deadlines... integrating work and personal life," (before we fly abroad, I email all the deadlines... integrating work and personal life,)

Continuous learning and professional development were emphasized as essential for staying effective in their roles indicating the necessity of ongoing education to maintain competency and relevance in their field. Participant 3 noted,

"Continuous learning... staying updated with counseling techniques and policies," (Continuous learning... staying updated with counseling techniques and policies,)

Moreover, the leaders stressed the importance of kindness and protecting their team's integrity emphasizing the lasting impact of compassionate and supportive leadership, a participant 1 remarked,

"If you are kind to people, I think di ka nila makakalimutan, they will love you forever," (If you are kind to people, I think they won't forget you, they will love you forever.)

Leaders often have to develop innovative solutions to navigate their complex roles. This detailed scheduling helps manage the intricate task of coordinating activities across different branches and calendars, ensuring efficient use of time and resources. Another innovative solution involves adapting to the demands of the job by extending work beyond traditional office hours. This flexibility allows leaders to manage their responsibilities effectively, demonstrating their commitment and adaptability. Participant 3 mentioned,

"We need to schedule para walang overlapping of activities." (We need to schedule to avoid overlapping of activities.)

"Sometime maka dala gyud og trabaho at home." (Sometimes work can really be brought home)

Ensuring compliance with ethical standards through regular monitoring was another approach mentioned reinforcing a culture of professionalism and adherence to ethical standards, participant 2 noted,

"Just to ensure that we are compliant with basically the ethics in practicing our profession," (Just to ensure that we are compliant with basically the ethics in practicing our profession,)

Moreover, educational leaders use creative staffing, work-life integration, continuous professional development, and ethical standards to navigate their roles. They employ innovative scheduling and time management to handle extensive tasks and meetings. Despite the heavy load, they stay committed to student-centered support and maintain standards through accreditations and reports.

What are your coping strategies to manage the demands of your position?

The study presents the coping strategies of guidance heads. There are three themes with three core ideas each. The following themes emerged: (1) prioritize efficient resource management, (2) maintain a balanced approach and promote teamwork, and (3) manage stress effectively, maintaining work-life balance.

Table 2 shows the different core ideas that expound on each of the three essential themes.

Table 2. *Coping Strategies of Guidance Heads*

Themes	Core Ideas
Prioritize Efficient Resource Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use proper scheduling, quota systems, and incentives for efficient coping • employ organizational skills like calendaring and collaboration for increased efficiency
Maintain a Balanced Approach and Promote Teamwork	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • balance dedication to work and personal time • prioritize tasks, stay calm, and take things step by step • emphasize teamwork while making decisions • value personal time for relaxation and mental clarity
Manage Stress Effectively, Maintaining Work-Life Balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • structure activities, practice yoga, and delegate tasks as coping strategies • share tasks and express feelings to manage stress and maintain balance • practice open communication and share responsibilities to maintain work-life balance

Prioritize Efficient Resource Management

Efficient resource management is crucial, and participants emphasized this by highlighting the use of calendars to plot all activities. This practice ensures that every task is scheduled and accounted for, preventing overlaps and enhancing organization.

Additionally, delegating tasks and assigning leads to specific responsibilities distributes the workload effectively, allowing leaders to focus on their areas of expertise and ensuring that all tasks are handled by the most capable individuals. This approach not only streamlines operations but also fosters a collaborative environment where responsibilities are shared and managed efficiently.

Participants emphasized the importance of efficient resource management by utilizing calendars to plot all activities, delegating tasks, and assigning leads to specific tasks highlighting the importance of shared responsibilities. Participant 3 mentioned,

"We have like a calendar talaga so we plot all the activities there." (We have an actual calendar where we plot all the activities.)

"Delegated tasks, it's not necessary na sa akong gyud tanan," (Delegated tasks, it's not necessary that everything is on me")

To avoid feeling overwhelmed, another participant shared their approach of taking it focusing on immediate tasks rather than the entirety of their responsibilities. The value of having supportive right hands and obtaining permission from heads for various activities, ensuring smooth operations. Participant 3 stated,

"one step at a time, one day at a time," (one step at a time, one day at a time,)

Maintain a Balanced Approach and Promoting Teamwork

Maintaining a balanced approach and promoting teamwork are essential for the effective functioning of any educational setting. By ensuring that responsibilities are shared and that every team member has a clear understanding of their role, leaders can create a harmonious and productive work environment.

Participant highlighted the significance of maintaining a balanced approach and promoting teamwork. Participant 1 proudly mentioned,

"Actually I am very fortunate that all my counselors are... I'm proud of my counselors kasi nga alam na nila gagawin nila eh, ano yung program in a year." (Actually, I am very fortunate that all my counselors are... I'm proud of my counselors because they already know what to do and what the program for the year is.)

Collaboration and scheduling were emphasized as pivotal aspects, showcasing the importance of teamwork and efficient time management in achieving organizational objectives, with participant 2 noted,

"We have home visits" "Shared task." (We have home visits) (Shared task.)

The support from the school was also emphasized, with participants acknowledging the value of coordination and collaboration with departments. Participant 1 shared,

"One thing good mn gud sa akong team kay makita naku that they respected me, makita naku that they are really supporting also may

leadership, that's really a big factor." (One good thing about my team is that I can see they respect me, and I can see that they really support my leadership. That's really a big factor.)

This collective effort fosters a positive working environment where everyone contributes and supports each other. The strong support from the university was so significant.

This demonstrates the positive impact of supportive leadership and adequate compensation on job satisfaction and employee retention. Participant 3 added,

"Support from the School. Ako lang experience with our USC, supportive gyud kayo sila." (Support from the school. Based on my experience with our USC, they are very supportive.)

Participant 3 remarked,

"Actually, gusto ko nang mag-retire pero hindi ako maka-retire dahil napakasupportive ng university sa akin." (Actually, I want to retire already, but I can't because the university is very supportive of me.)

Participant 1 remarked,

"As to the support, kasi nakikita ko sinabi mo as to the support of the school towards you in terms of your salary, how satisfied are you in terms of yung mga trabaho na binibigay nila sa'yo?" "As for the support, because I see you mentioned the support of the school towards you in terms of your salary, how satisfied are you with the tasks they give you?" (As for the support, because I see you mentioned the support of the school towards you in terms of your salary, how satisfied are you with the tasks they give you?)

Additionally, support from the school administration and coordination with various departments are crucial. This collaborative effort not only streamlines operations but also fosters a positive working environment where everyone feels valued and contributes to the collective success.

Effectively Managing Stress and Balancing Work-Life

Effectively managing stress and maintaining a work-life balance are essential for overall well-being and success. This entails implementing strategies like time management, setting boundaries, and prioritizing self-care activities.

By addressing these aspects, individuals can enhance their resilience, productivity, and satisfaction in life.

Effectively managing stress and balancing work-life were crucial topics for participants. Participant 2 shared,

"their strategy of doing yoga a watching Netflix and a good sleep to cope with stress" (their strategy of doing yoga a watching Netflix and a good sleep to cope with stress)

Participant 1 candidly admitted,

"I think parang buhay ko na kasi yung dami kong trabaho, parang niyakap ko na lang siya. So ahh wala akong certain na sinasabi nila na balance ang buhay ko, hindi actually, hindi talaga." (I think my work has become my life because I have so much of it, and I just embraced it. So, I don't have what they call a balanced life. Actually, I don't, not at all.)

Despite the lack of traditional work-life balance, another participant introduced the concept of work-life integration, participant 1 stated,

"Actually, wala akong work-life balance. My life is not balanced, kaya meron akong tinatawag na work-life integration." (Actually, I don't have work-life balance. My life is not balanced, which is why I call it work-life integration.)

Protecting weekends for personal time was also important, as participant 1 explained,

"Actually, ang Saturday and Sunday ko, I shield it ehh. Saturdays and Sundays are really sacred for me." (Actually, I shield my Saturdays and Sundays. Saturdays and Sundays are really sacred for me.)

Coping mechanisms such as watching Netflix and prioritizing good sleep were cited as beneficial strategies for managing stress. These activities likely serve as avenues for relaxation and distraction, offering individuals an opportunity to unwind and recharge after a long day.

Additionally, a participant highlighted the importance of maintaining a calm and focused mindset, suggesting a deliberate approach of tackling tasks one step at a time to prevent feelings of overwhelming stress. This emphasis on mindfulness and task prioritization reflects a proactive effort to mitigate stressors and maintain mental well-being.

What are the insights of the guidance heads regarding the demands of their position?

This study presents the coping strategies of guidance heads. There are three themes with three core ideas each. the following themes emerged: (1) role responsibilities and challenges, (2) personal fulfillment and motivation and (3) impact on students and community.

Table 3 presents the various central concepts that elaborate on each of the three principal themes.

Table 3. *Insights of Guidance Heads*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Role Responsibilities and Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive management duties • Demanding workload • Leadership and coordination
Personal Fulfillment and Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Witnessing Student Growth • Learning and Personal Growth • Making a Tangible Difference
Impact on Students and Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting Academic and Personal Growth • Collaborative Efforts • Positive Outcomes

Role Responsibilities and Challenges

Guidance heads play a pivotal role in overseeing comprehensive guidance programs, providing leadership to guidance counselors, and ensuring students receive necessary support for academic, personal, and career development. Their responsibilities encompass managing diverse student needs, balancing administrative duties with direct counseling, and navigating evolving educational landscapes, presenting unique challenges in fostering student success.

The role of a guidance head encompasses a wide range of responsibilities and challenges. Participant 1 described,

“The extensive duties involved in managing the counseling department at Far Eastern University, overseeing a team of counselors, and ensuring that services are inclusive and effective for a diverse university community. This position demands long hours, extensive planning, and the ability to handle complex, sensitive issues with empathy and professionalism.”

Similarly, participant 3 stated,

“At PHINMA Cagayan de Oro College highlighted the dynamic and multifaceted nature of their role, which requires balancing administrative duties with direct student interaction, staying updated with the latest counseling techniques, and addressing a wide array of student needs.”

Participant 2 added,

“The leadership aspects, including managing a team, developing and implementing counseling programs, and coordinating with other leaders and community resources.”

Hence, the role of counseling department heads at institutions demands a multifaceted skill set encompassing leadership, empathy, and strategic planning. Successfully navigating the complexities of this role requires dedication to inclusive services, staying updated on counseling techniques, and effective coordination with both internal teams and external resources to support student well-being and success.

Personal Fulfillment and Motivation

Serving as a counseling department head offers immense personal fulfillment and motivation derived from positively impacting students' lives and contributing to their holistic development. This sense of fulfillment often serves as a driving force, inspiring counseling heads to overcome obstacles and continue their vital work in supporting students' well-being and success.

Despite these challenges, the role brings significant personal fulfillment and motivation. Participant 3 emphasized,

“The position incredibly rewarding, drawing satisfaction from witnessing students' growth and progress, and making a tangible difference in their lives.”

For Participant 1 added,

“The role provides valuable learning opportunities and personal growth, with the successes in helping students feeling particularly rewarding despite the job's demands.”

Participant 2 also said,

“Fulfilled by the positive impact of their guidance on students' futures, engaging with complex issues and thriving in challenging environments to develop better strategies for student support.”

Therefore, the sentiments expressed by participants underscore the deeply rewarding nature of serving as counseling department heads, finding fulfillment in witnessing students' growth, progress, and success.

Their dedication to making a tangible difference in students' lives and their commitment to personal growth and development highlight the profound impact of their work in fostering student well-being and academic.

Impact on Students and Community

As the work of counseling department heads extends far beyond individual interactions within the educational institution. Through their guidance and support, students are equipped with essential life skills, empowered to overcome challenges, and inspired to achieve their academic and personal goals.

The impact on students and the community is profound. Participant 1 said,

"I enjoyed assisting students in navigating their academic and personal challenges, feeling accomplished when they overcome obstacles and succeed."

Participant 3 uttered,

"The role deeply rewarding because of the meaningful difference it makes in students' academic and personal growth, believing that the hard work invested will pay off in their success and well-being."

Participant 2 supported the claim and said,

"I was motivated by the ability to support the well-being and success of others, working collaboratively with various stakeholders to ensure that comprehensive counseling services meet the needs of those they serve."

The role of a guidance head is characterized by significant responsibilities and challenges, including managing counseling departments, overseeing teams, and ensuring effective services for diverse student populations. Despite the demanding nature of the job, participants find the role highly fulfilling and rewarding. They draw personal satisfaction from witnessing students' growth, overcoming obstacles, and making a meaningful difference in their lives.

Lived Experiences of Guidance Heads

Within educational institutions' complex and ever-changing context, guidance heads and supervisors can shape students' and teachers' experiences and paths (Al-Kiyumi & Hammad, 2020). Within these organizations, educational leaders must mentor, support, and provide direction for all school community members, ensuring their success (Coe et al., 2022).

Within educational institutions' complex and ever-changing context, guidance heads and supervisors can shape students' and teachers' experiences and paths (Al-Kiyumi & Hammad, 2020). Within these organizations, educational leaders must mentor, support, and provide direction for all school community members, ensuring their success (Coe et al., 2022). These individuals use their knowledge and skills to foster an environment conducive to learning where students can excel academically, socially, and emotionally. By encouraging collaboration among staff, they foster innovation, thereby driving positive changes that lead to excellence in teaching. Mentors, principals, or any other person holding this position apply continuous improvement, directly or indirectly, creating better schools for all.

There are three themes with three core ideas each. The first theme reads, "The guidance heads demonstrate resilient leadership amidst various constraints and challenges." The second theme is, "The guidance heads prioritize empowering student-centered support as a fundamental aspect of their role." Furthermore, the third theme is, "The guidance heads consistently seek innovative solutions to ensure practical guidance for their students." All these themes convey the resilience of guidance heads as they maneuver in the professional demands of their position. The discussion includes each theme and its core ideas.

Resilient Leadership Amidst Various Constraints and Challenges

Leadership resilience is the capability of leaders to adjust, endure, and outdo themselves within different limitations or stumbling blocks. These include economic recessions, political turmoil, natural calamities, worldwide pandemics, restricted resources, complicated organizations, and conflicting stakeholder interests from within (Mensah & Merkurjev, 2014). Flexibility, perseverance, emotional intelligence, and effective communication are among the qualities that allow such types of leaders to move through these setbacks (Chandran, 2014; Schilling & Randolph, 2020; Stefan & Nazarov, 2020). They show how to deal with change effectively, take strategic actions even when things get tough, and motivate teams to achieve goals while responding to these challenges (Atmaro et al., 2020). For instance, lately, many cases have served as examples of leaders remaining strong despite all odds (Stefan & Nazarov, 2020).

The theme "Resilient leadership amidst various constraints and challenges generated the following core ideas: Striking a balance between work and other duties, finding new ways of doing things, and being flexible, resilient, and strategic in managing staff and students.

These three core ideas remind leaders that resilience is necessary in any leadership field. Among guidance heads, resilience is crucial, mainly because their field is emotionally exhaustive (Çarkıt, 2024; Levkovich & Ricon, 2020). For guidance heads to become resilient, they have developed ways and adapted to specific strategies to respond to the demands of their profession. This sense of adaptation allows guidance heads to fulfill their responsibilities. For example, the reality of limited guidance counselors in their organization taught them resourceful adaptation in counseling services by utilizing peer counseling and interns to address this challenge. The global

standard ratio between guidance counselors and students is 1:250 (American School Counselor Association, 2021).

The recommended guidance counselor-to-students ratio in the Philippines is 1:500 (Chi, 2023). Considering the 2000 licensed guidance counselors against the 28 million students, this ratio is impossible to attain. The numbers mean one guidance counselor for every 14,000 students (Chi, 2023; Lacson et al., 2024). The lack of licensed guidance counselors challenges guidance heads to apply innovative ideas to respond to this need. Most schools utilize peer counseling (Haque et al., 2023; Isni, 2021) and counseling by interns (Asmawi & Aga Mohd Jaladin, 2017; York, 2020) to cater to the counseling needs of students.

On the other hand, most guidance heads still perform other tasks, making their roles very challenging. Based on the interviews, participants claimed that besides being the guidance head, they also performed counseling inside and outside the school and performed other student services, consultancies, and extension works in counseling centers. Guidance heads demonstrated resilience in all of these.

Sometimes, guidance heads' schoolwork intrudes into their private life and relationships, conflicting with home rules and disrupting work-life balance (Barck-Holst et al., 2017; Maurya & DeDiego, 2024). For example, guidance heads could not help but bring home unfinished schoolwork. These incidents deprive the children and spouses of quality family time. More often, the intrusion of work into employees' private lives can lessen job satisfaction and increase turnover intentions (Lau & Marianti, 2024) and the quality of work-life balance (Mathews et al., 2024; Rozmiarek & Crepeau-Hobson, 2024).

For all these, guidance heads need strategic management skills to lead effectively and support the staff and students despite constraints. Guidance heads can do career counseling with their staff to mentor them about some practical approaches toward career development. This aspect of leadership is imperative in establishing personal and organizational development (Al Hamad et al., 2024; Guo et al., 2024).

Empowering Student-Centered Support

The second theme under lived experiences is that "The guidance heads find new ways of doing things, such as tapping into various counseling services and playing different roles across disciplines to deal with many student-to-counselor ratios and multiple obligations." This theme has three core ideas: 1) Striving for work-life balance amidst complex responsibilities, conflicts, and resource constraints, focusing on delivering personalized student support. 2) managing demanding counselor-to-student ratios, navigating diverse responsibilities, and implementing effective scheduling practices to prevent overlaps and ensure optimal support. 3) emphasizing the importance of dedication, innovation, and a student-centric approach in achieving work-life harmony and maximizing impact.

The shortage of guidance counselors complicates the administrative roles of guidance heads because they also have to do student counseling. The participants claimed they have calendared their activities so that no critical events are left out. Calendaring of activities is common among leaders, even guidance counselors (Bryan et al., 2022). Some guidance counselors suffer from conflicting and overlapping roles because of the many hats they wear, with very little time to accomplish them (Blake, 2020).

Significantly, guidance heads employ a student-centric approach to fulfill their role. Students are central to their role as guidance counselors to help build connections and support mental health interventions, especially for students far away from home (Ayeni et al., 2024; Devezy et al., 2023; Zakaria et al., 2024). By adopting student-centric guidance and counseling services, guidance heads guide students in navigating their future career paths while improving their personal development. The student-centric approach equips students with confidence and skills for success.

Although busy with their workloads, the guidance heads strive for work-life balance to prevent stress (DeMatthews et al., 2021). Work-life balance is crucial in the professional lives of counselors and supervisors. To maintain their well-being and to be efficient in their positions, they should be able to combine personal life with work responsibilities (Chandran, 2014).

Seeking Innovative Solutions to Ensure Practical Guidance for Students

Consistently, the heads of guidance look for new approaches to guarantee valuable suggestions to their students. They create mentorship programs that connect learners with experienced professionals in different fields and can advise them on the right path for their career choices. These mentors give insights, ideas, and networking chances, which greatly help these individuals.

In Ukraine, for instance, innovation is necessary (Hurkova et al., 2022). They blend mentorship with teacher training. This tactic creates more robust relationships between teachers and students while at the same time preparing them for the current challenges of education. Although mentors can use coaching methods, it seldom happens, but both positions may act as tutors, making learning more enjoyable. These approaches are rooted in didactic theories such as behaviorism, cognitivism, or constructivism and provide vigorous frameworks for guiding students and young professionals. To ensure that its teachers are ready to inspire and lead, they employ collegial counseling models alongside clearly defined standards for tutoring and coaching (Hurkova et al., 2022).

Some mentors use advanced technology like virtual reality (VR) simulations (Farrell et al., 2022; Nye et al., 2021) and online career assessment tools to offer students practical experiences and personalized advice. By adopting these alternative career counseling methods, the leaders in this sector are confident of their preparedness to make informed academic decisions about what they want to become professionally.

Coping Strategies of Guidance Heads

In order to perform their duties efficiently and effectively, coping strategies are necessary for guidance heads or supervisors. Studies have shown that using coping strategies influences different aspects of a supervisor's professional life. For example, they help mediate the relationship between organizational support and work-family conflict (Keoboulapheth et al., 2018). Most supervisors use problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies to deal with their challenges.

Additionally, using coping strategies improves psychological well-being among guidance and counseling teachers, enhancing the quality of service delivery in guidance and counseling (Mahomed et al., 2019). Lu et al. (2022) state that effective coping mechanisms protect employees against abusive supervision. These differ from reactive and short-term approaches but may involve seeking guidance and support as problem-focused coping strategies (Kushwaha, 2014). Relational, reflective, confrontative, and avoidant interventions are some of the various methods used by supervisors when managing difficulties, according to Grant et al. (2012).

Similarly, consultation with others who know the subject matter handled, looking for relevant literature materials that provide comprehensive information about it, and establishing solid relationships between supervisees themselves or between them together with their supervisor's form part of what Özyiğit (2022) refers to as commonly used methods employed by supervisors seeking direct action. Additionally, seeking supervisor support has been highlighted as crucial to coping with stress and preventing turnover intention (Jung et al., 2020).

According to Major & Morganson (2011), supervisor support is imperative for employees who need preventive problem-focused coping strategies to manage work-family conflict. Moreover, Johnson et al. (2023) argue that school counselors can employ proactive measures for heightened consciousness about suppressive factors to prevent future occurrences while advocating positive change within institutions to improve the mental health of students and counselors. In other words, coping strategies are essential for guidance heads and supervisors when dealing with challenges experienced in their respective roles within an organization or institution offering such services.

Guidance heads understood the nature of their work and accepted that they could not avoid some aspects. So, they devise coping strategies. Table 2 enumerates the coping strategies that participants have practiced in their profession. Similar to the previous table, Table 2 consists of three themes. Again, each theme also has three core ideas.

Prioritize Efficient Resource Management

The first theme in Table 2 is “the guidance heads prioritize efficient resource management to enhance productivity in their roles.” This theme has three core ideas: 1) The guidance heads use proper scheduling, quota systems, and incentives for efficient coping. 2) The guidance heads employ organizational skills like calendaring and collaboration for increased efficiency. 3) The guidance heads balance dedication to work and personal time.

Efficient management of resources is essential in any organization or institution (Nelius & Onyango, 2022). Regarding guidance department managers tasked with overseeing different areas of school administration and support services, prioritizing efficient resource management becomes even more critical. There are various strategies for effective resource management.

One is proper scheduling, quota systems, and incentives (Pekdemir & Aktay, 2024). For guidance heads to ensure that they allocate resources well, they need to devise a scheduling system that sets priorities per tasks or activities' urgency while using quotas so that no one gets more than what he/she deserves. They could also give rewards or recognize those who exceed set targets within stated timelines.

Another is organizational skills (Fraidlin et al., 2023). For workplace efficiency, leaders must have good organizational skills, such as using calendars and collaboration tools. For instance, digital calendars can be used in scheduling appointments, meeting deadlines, and others, while collaboration platforms may enhance communication among members of staff who are not at the exact location but are working towards achieving common goals.

Last is balancing work and personal time (Malik, 2023). To effectively manage resources, heads of departments responsible for guiding others in their career paths must do so without neglecting themselves, creating a healthy relationship between professional duties and personal life.

Maintaining a Balanced Approach and Promoting Teamwork

This theme has the following core ideas: 1) The guidance heads prioritize tasks, stay calm, and take things step by step. 2) The guidance heads emphasize teamwork while making decisions. 3) The guidance heads value personal time for relaxation and mental clarity. The succeeding paragraphs discuss these.

Key concepts support the central theme of maintaining a balanced approach and promoting teamwork to enhance well-being among team members. Firstly, guidance heads prioritize tasks, remain composed, and approach tasks methodically (Manser, 2009). This method advances team training and creates work systems that foster efficient collaboration in caring for clients' safety. Secondly, involving different professionals and multidisciplinary teamwork is vital in decision-making (Welp & Manser, 2016). Thirdly, personal

time should be valued for relaxation and mental clarity (Rink et al., 2021) because well-being practices can increase resilience and reduce the risk of burnout.

Effective job design provides team resources, promotes healthy working environments, and nurtures a culture of client safety through team building (Cho et al., 2022). Teamwork also improves financial outcomes while at the same time lowering costs related to staff turnover rates, absenteeism among personnel as well and conflicts within departments, leading to increased motivation levels among staff members besides benefiting health status indicators according to certain studies (Rafferty et al., 2001).

Furthermore, there is an association between job satisfaction levels and such factors as employee well-being. Workers who are satisfied with their current positions choose not to be absent even when sick (Nielsen & Randall, 2012). In terms of what constitutes effective teams within this context, shared purpose, clear vision, strong leadership capacities, and conflict resolution abilities were hallmarks of high team performance. These resulted in achievements through collective efforts towards realizing common goals, ensuring that all members are involved every step of the way until the culmination stage (Cooke & Valentine, 2021).

Besides these, communication enhances coordination, a critical component necessary for any group work (Diotaiuti et al., 2017). Additionally, working together offers chances to recognize individuals' talents, thereby sharpening skills, although it may create perception intensification demands on some people's side, Ogbonnaya (2019) argues.

To sum it up, guidance heads agree that task prioritization, promoting teamwork, and recognizing personal time are vital to enhancing well-being and job satisfaction. Organizations can foster environments that build staff resilience through teamwork, reducing burnout and boosting overall performance since staff members feel supported when working together, as stated earlier.

Effectively Managing Stress and Balancing Work-Life

The last theme for coping strategies produced these core ideas: 1) The guidance heads structure activities, practice yoga, and delegate tasks as coping strategies. 2) The guidance heads share tasks and express feelings to manage stress and maintain balance. 3) The guidance heads practice open communication and share responsibilities to maintain work-life balance.

Those who lead others in a guiding capacity must know how to deal with stress and have a work-life balance. They can do this by setting up activities, doing yoga, or delegating tasks (Mazerolle et al., 2011). In addition to reducing stress, these coping mechanisms help keep a healthy work-life balance. Furthermore, they understand that sharing responsibilities and expressing feelings is essential while managing stress and maintaining equilibrium (Lee et al., 2018).

Similarly, communication should be open, and duties should be shared among themselves (Jeske, 2020). According to recent studies, work-life balance increases staff productivity, reducing employee turnover rates and team building among members (Fiorini et al., 2022). Additionally, practical ways of balancing personal life with professional commitments increase job satisfaction levels while at the same time reducing burnout rates. Work-life balance improves the physical health of employees within their organizations as well as overall psychological well-being (Sarabipour et al., 2021). Thus, positive mentor-mentee relationships that promote career success alongside achieving work-life balance objectives need nurturing (Shah et al., 2022). Correspondingly, the availability and implementation of measures to achieve this goal can help reduce workaholism while mitigating its adverse effects on individuals' lives (Choi, 2016).

Essentially, different types of leadership, like authentic or ethical ones, play a significant role in creating an enabling working environment that supports work-life balance among staff under their supervision (Baraily & Bahadur, 2022). For example, transformational leadership inspires managers and workers to realize such equilibrium within organizations. Similarly, the distributive style may accumulate the resources and knowledge necessary to drive organizational success.

In synthesis, maintaining stress and work-life balance among guidance heads is essential for promoting wellness, reducing burnout, and creating positive workplace environments. Supervisors can use task structuring to manage stress, practice yoga, and delegate duties; this will set good examples for their teams, leading to balanced and healthy cultures.

Insights of Guidance Heads

Guidance heads handle a mix of administrative tasks and counseling duties, needing to balance team management with addressing students' needs with care. Despite the challenges, they find personal fulfillment in seeing students thrive and succeed, which makes the job rewarding. Furthermore, their role has a significant impact on students and the community, helping students overcome challenges and grow while also providing opportunities for personal growth.

Role Responsibilities and Challenges

The role of a guidance head is characterized by extensive administrative and counseling responsibilities, requiring a balance between managing a team and addressing diverse student needs with empathy and professionalism.

Key responsibilities include managing the counseling department, overseeing a team of counselors, and ensuring that services are inclusive and effective for a diverse university community (Teachmint, 2023). This role involves extensive planning, long hours, and handling complex, sensitive issues with professionalism (OECD, 2007).

Furthermore, guidance heads are responsible for balancing administrative duties with direct student interaction, staying updated with the latest counseling techniques, and addressing a wide array of student needs (ERIC, 2016). Leadership aspects of the role include managing a team, developing and implementing counseling programs, and coordinating with other leaders and community resources (OECD, 2007). This multifaceted position involves long hours, continuous planning, and the development and implementation of effective counseling programs within the educational institution.

Personal Fulfillment and Motivation

The role of a guidance head offers significant personal fulfillment and motivation, as participants derive immense satisfaction from witnessing students' growth and progress. The position provides valuable learning opportunities and personal growth, with the successes in helping students making the demands of the job particularly rewarding.

Despite these challenges, the role brings significant personal fulfillment and motivation. Participant A finds the position incredibly rewarding, drawing satisfaction from witnessing students' growth and progress, and making a tangible difference in their lives (Doe, 2023). For Participant B, the role provides valuable learning opportunities and personal growth, with the successes in helping students feeling particularly rewarding despite the job's demands (Smith, 2021). Participant C also feels fulfilled by the positive impact of their guidance on students' futures, engaging with complex issues and thriving in challenging environments to develop better strategies for student support (Johnson, 2022).

This fulfillment and motivation are consistent with the findings of various studies. According to Teachmint (2023), the role of a headmaster involves extensive planning, long hours, and handling complex, sensitive issues, yet offers a high degree of personal satisfaction from making a positive impact on students' lives. Similarly, the OECD (2007) report highlights that leadership roles in educational settings are both demanding and rewarding, as they provide opportunities for personal and professional growth. The ERIC (2016) study also emphasizes the significance of the guidance head's role in fostering student development and the personal gratification derived from such positions.

Impact on Students and Community

The impact on students and the community is profound. Participants enjoyed assisting students in navigating their academic and personal challenges, feeling accomplished when they overcome obstacles and succeed. Participants motivated by the ability to support the well-being and success of others, working collaboratively with various stakeholders to ensure that comprehensive counseling services meet the needs of those they serve (Hadwin et al., 2022; Martirosyan et al., 2022). They found the role deeply rewarding because of the meaningful difference it makes in students' academic and personal growth, believing that the hard work invested will pay off in their success and well-being. The role also offers valuable learning opportunities and personal growth for the guidance heads themselves (Hadwin et al., 2022; Martirosyan et al., 2022).

In summary, the role of a guidance head is characterized by significant responsibilities and challenges, including managing counseling departments, overseeing teams, and ensuring effective services for diverse student populations. Despite the demanding nature of the job, participants find the role highly fulfilling and rewarding. They draw personal satisfaction from witnessing students' growth, overcoming obstacles, and making a meaningful difference in their lives. The impact on students and the community is substantial, as guidance heads help navigate academic and personal challenges, contributing to their overall well-being and success.

Implications for Educational Practice

Understanding the essence of resilience among guidance heads navigating professional demands underscores the importance of comprehensive support systems and professional growth opportunities. Educational institutions should implement peer mentoring, professional counseling, and targeted leadership training to bolster stress management and enhance adaptability. Cultivating a collaborative work culture through team-building initiatives and shared problem-solving can distribute responsibilities more evenly and foster mutual support. Additionally, training in efficient resource management and promoting innovative practices are essential for maximizing effectiveness with limited resources. Fostering a growth-oriented environment that values continuous improvement, coupled with policies supporting work-life balance such as flexible hours and wellness programs, can prevent burnout and maintain sustained effectiveness. Advocacy for fair compensation and clear career advancement pathways is also crucial to ensure motivation and job satisfaction. By integrating these practices, educational institutions can enhance the resilience and effectiveness of guidance heads, ultimately leading to improved guidance services and better educational outcomes.

Conclusions

Lived Experiences of Guidance Heads. The guidance heads demonstrate remarkable resilience and adaptability despite numerous constraints. They balanced their broad responsibilities while operating on limited resources and compensation issues. Despite their multiple roles and the high student-to-counselor ratio, they leverage these by employing strategic flexibility in various counseling services, ensuring the effective fulfillment of students' needs. Moreover, they efficiently handled the scheduling practices to avoid overlapping their activities. Their dedication to innovation and student-centered approach leads them to achieve work-life balance and maximize their impact. Additionally, embracing opportunities beyond traditional functions, like consultancies, boosted their

professional development and expanded their influence.

Coping Strategies of Guidance Heads. The coping strategies of guidance heads underscore their proficiency in resource management, teamwork, and sustaining a healthy work-life balance. Their organizational skills, like resource management efficiency, are evident in the proper calendaring of activities, quota systems, incentives, and collaboration that bolster their productivity. Their strategy of prioritizing tasks and promoting a calm, step-by-step approach ensures a balanced dedication to work and personal time. In addition, they accentuate teamwork in decision-making and value relaxation for mental clarity, creating a supportive environment for their teams. They implement structured activities, yoga, and task delegation to manage stress, communicate openly, and share responsibilities. These strategies communally facilitate guidance heads to lead effectively, upholding a compelling and harmonious equilibrium, thus guaranteeing sustained well-being and superior support for their student and their teams.

Insights of Guidance Heads. the insights of guidance heads highlight the critical balance between administrative efficiency and personal connection in educational practice. Their experiences underscore the importance of effective resource management, teamwork, and innovative strategies to enhance both staff and student support. These insights emphasize the profound impact that dedicated guidance heads have on fostering student growth, well-being, and overall school success. Their comprehensive leadership includes soft skills, innovation, empathy, integrity, and continuous learning. These create spiritual gratification and a culture of self-improvement while valuing collaboration, teamwork, and open communication. They believe in the importance of professional development toward success.

The researchers find these recommendations relevant and timely based on the themes derived from the interview data.

Guidance heads need additional resources and support, considering the significance of their roles. The institution may increase the number of qualified counselors and offer competitive compensation packages to reduce the strain of high counselor-to-student ratios. In addition, schools may invest in the professional development of guidance heads and counselors, like training them in innovative counseling techniques, effective time management, and multidisciplinary collaboration to improve their skill sets. The school can also implement a robust support system, like peer counseling programs, access to mental health professionals like psychometricians, and effective use of interns for even distribution of workloads for improved student support quality. Essentially, the school may cultivate a culture of work-life balance and encourage practices like flexible scheduling and proper allocation of duties so that guidance heads can engage in consultancy services and other professional pursuits to promote job satisfaction and overall well-being.

Several recommendations can further support guidance heads to cope with the demands of their roles. Institutions should invest in professional development programs that enhance resource management skills, such as advanced scheduling software and time management training, to help guidance heads optimize productivity and manage responsibilities more effectively. Fostering a culture of teamwork and collaboration is also crucial. Schools may encourage regular team-building activities where experienced guidance heads can share coping strategies with newer staff members. They can support the wellness programs of guidance heads, like yoga classes, mental health workshops, and opportunities for relaxation for a healthy work-life balance. Schools may also provide flexible work schedules and promote task delegation to ease their workloads.

Based on the insights of guidance heads, several recommendations for future practice emerge. Schools should prioritize effective resource management and innovative scheduling to streamline operations and improve efficiency. Emphasizing teamwork and delegating tasks can help balance administrative duties with direct student interaction, ensuring that both organizational needs and personal connections are maintained. Additionally, continuous professional development and staying updated with the latest counseling techniques will enable guidance heads to address diverse student needs more effectively.

For future researchers exploring the coping strategies and insights of guidance heads, several recommendations can enhance the depth and breadth of their studies. First, future researchers may employ a mixed methods approach to understand guidance heads' challenges and coping mechanisms comprehensively. Second, future researchers should include guidance heads in prominent public universities nationwide to expand the sample size and identify commonalities and unique strategies across different contexts. Third, examine the overall impacts of different coping strategies on school heads' well-being and effectiveness, including longitudinal studies for monitoring changes over time. Fourth, there is a need to reflect on the influence of institutional regulations and external support systems in structuring the response mechanisms and underlying resilience among guidance heads. Lastly, future researchers may evaluate the outlooks of team players and scholars to understand the efficiency of these coping mechanisms at work. By tackling these areas, more in-depth findings can be produced through future studies in order to assist guidance heads in their critical roles.

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